

IMIA WG 6 `Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (previously known as Medical Concept Representation)

History:

The working group is mentioned as early as in the 1981 IMIA report for the General Assembly, where formation of working groups has been agreed upon. Since then, the WG was charged with: (1) Reviewing health data nomenclature and classification needs for the world community; (2) Evaluating information processing technology; and (3) Recommending methods for future classification and nomenclature systems. A short history reveals significant milestones:

Eighties and nineties

The name of the WG was "The Role of Informatics in the Classification and Coding of Health Data", later "Coding and Classification of Data". It was chaired by RA Cote, later by JR. Scherrer, followed by C.Chute. A series of successful WG meetings resulted in proceedings - see the literature pages on this wiki.

Years 2000-2010

In the next decade the main milestones have been the following:

- Joint panels on Terminology and Natural Language Processing, Medinfo 2004 with MIE and AMIA working groups.
- A meeting in Rome, Italy from April 29-May 2, 2005. Barry Smith of the University of Buffalo was Program Chair. Proceedings appeared in the Journal of Biomedical Informatics as a special issue of the Journal of Biomedical computing in June, 2006.
- Olivier Bodenreider took over chairmanship in from the second half of the decade. See his comprehensive overview of the domain in 2006 here: <http://bib.oxfordjournals.org/content/7/3/256.full>

Recent activities:

The WG convened at MEDINFO 2010 in Cape Town to plan further activities. Recent activities (2011-2012) have been reported in our LinkedIn group and at our content site. The LinkedIn group was formed as one of the decided steps to reach out to the professional/scientific community with an interest in the topics addressed by this working group.

Goal and operations of the LinkedIn Group:

The aim of the IMIA LinkedIn Group on Medical Concept Representation (LI WG LaMB (formerly MCR) is to provide a platform neutral, high level forum to discuss emerging professional issues, to promote relevant events and publications, to connect interested individuals to influential people in the domain. We hope that the WG MCR, now LaMB will grow to an orientation point for professionals on this network in the area of medical concept representations. Ideas, suggestions are more than welcome! Please check the LinkedIn group and below described the content site for upcoming news and events. See details here:

<http://www.linkedin.com/groups/IMIA-Medical-Concept-Representation-Working-3680642/about>

Goal and operations of LaMB WG content site:

Reports of ongoing business meetings are published at our wiki site, where we have also published the documents of our history. The content site will host all information we would like to share with interested partners. We also hope to get input from the research & professional community. The content site is [here](#).

Stefan Schulz chair

Laszlo Balkanyi – co chair and group admin

Olivier Bodenreider past chair

Ronald Cornet, active member

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